

ANALYSING MORAL BEHAVIOURS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WHO ARE DOING SPORTS OR NOT

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research was to determine the moral behaviour in terms of some variables of the students who are participating in school sports or not. In this research participated in totally 191 students, all of them having education at different educational situation in Burdur city centre. "Sportmanship Scale for Physical Education Lesson" developed by KOC.SPSS 22.0 and Mplus 7.0 Windows programmes were used in statistical analysis of data obtained from research. In the end of the research, independent samples T-test was applied for students' morally behavior, for the sports games in order to know whether there are differences by gender or not. According to the analysis result, there are no differences between male and female students' moral conduct score. For understanding the effects of age groups of the students, 6th, 7th and 8th grades were compared using "Analysis of Variance" (ANOVA). This comparison results showed meaningful differentiation for age groups of the students' moral behaviour in sports games. At the same time students who attended both physical education lesson and school competitions had a significant difference in scores of appropriate behaviour. As a result, students who participate in competitions have more appropriate behaviour score than the ones which only participate in physical education lessons.

Keywords: ethics, sportmanship, secondary school students, school sports, sports ethics

1. Introduction

The aim of the study "*Analysing Moral Behaviours of Secondary School Students Who Are Doing Sports or Not*" is to analyse the impact of the sports on the moral attitudes of the students who participate in sports or not. Human beings undergo constant change and development during their lifespan. We may easily say that key changes and major

developments occur in adolescence period. In this period, individuals possess the physical, mental, spiritual, and social characteristics as well as the skills to gain a place in society.

Having a healthy adolescence period compatible with the “expected behaviour” is important for both individuals and society. Otherwise, unexpected social outcome” will cause harm to individuals and society as well [Kırımoglu H. 2008]. Fair-play is usually considered as a part or principle of “ethics”. The phenomenon of ethics embodies principles such as showing sensitivity to individual's needs and differences, having personal responsibility, sympathy towards the “other”, trustworthiness, and adherence to fair-play. In terms of sports, the concept of fair-play comprises and embodies “higher” and universal values. Having the highest values is the last step of being human [Öngel, H. B. 1997].

The activities in physical education form and shape the students' interest, perspective and abilities. Games played at right time serve to the physical improvement of the students and contribute to their social progress and adaptation to their environment as well. A sport event creates a collectivity consisted mainly of sportsman, teachers, specialist consultants, managers, public sports institutions, audiences and sports media. Inadequacy in any one of these elements or breakage of the connection among the ones directly linked will affect others negatively. Merits of the sports will be destroyed no matter how much the students are educated and disciplined in accordance with the essence of sports if the teacher, trainer or principals of the schools lay down success as a condition in order to popularize their team, school, or region or to pursue their own personal interests.

Sports training should always be available to the youth and even being promoted to whole society. Having sport training is a civil right. And, it is only possible to mention about “merits of sports” for all institutions involved in “sport events” when this right is equally exercised [Erdemli, A. 2006]. Apart from the rules of competition – written or not – one should always comply with the concepts of “fairness” and “virtuousness”. This, by helping the “fair-play”, the “emerge and develop” and by protecting individuals and sporters from danger, will help them be virtuous [Atesoglu, M.1974]. Physical education courses and school competitions should be used as a lever to reinforce attitudes and behaviours conforming to “fair play”.

Turkey is not the only country facing problems and inadequacies in this field. European Fair Play Movement with a declaration in a plenary session pointed out that formal education officials are responsible for communicating the concepts of fair-play, tolerance, virtuousness, mutual respect to the students and they suggested national governments include fair-play into physical education curriculum and principals of the schools, trainers and teachers use materials that help students internalize fair-play [Yildiran, 2004].

Education embodies specific goal-oriented activities and for that reason, schools – being educational institutions- are places to provide and deliver education. Schools are generally considered as places to provide formal education [Bilen, M. 2002]. Education officials have tremendous responsibility while accomplishing the educational

objectives. Education officials should apply rules to everyone equally. They should treat individuals equally and provide them remuneration for their efforts. They should be fair to individuals and hold the scales even. They should resolve conflicts among his subordinates without bias. They should endeavour to ensure fairness. They should charge the penalty proportioned to the fault. They should ensure that individuals use their legal rights. They should conduct objective assessment. They should take care to avoid the actions that will cause harm to individuals [Gültekin, M. 2008]. Every human activity performed should have creative, formative aspects and contribute to competence. Children, for the first time experience sport activities at primary schooldays. At this stage, it is important that the teachers who introduce sports to students should be sports training specialists. Through the sport activities at schools, young individuals build physical, intellectual and social awareness. With this kind of awareness, new values will be acquired both in social relations and sports [Sahin, M. 2007]. School sports are the activity syllabuses carried out at primary and high schools, universities and other institutes. These syllabuses aim the improvement of the skills and ability of the students and are designed accordingly. School sports are put into practice by voluntary participation in competitions, open-air activities, and physical fitness activities [Bucher Charles A. 1987]. The period of the physical growth and development of children and young individuals, coincide with the schooldays. In this period, to form some habits and to have agility and strength by getting involved in sports activities seems crucial. To lessen the pressure and depression created by rapid urbanization and other living conditions and to cushion the physical and moral effects of these conditions on human, and to create more healthy society, physical education and sports activities should be turned into an indispensable habit in life. Primary and secondary school students are the most suitable age group for this crucial step [Meb, 2006]. Every single individual may participate in sports. But, sport activities and fair-play would only be meaningful when the participants have gained the merits such as having self-respect, having respect to "others", being unselfish, asserting his/her rights [Sahin, M. 2007]. Ethics is a part of philosophy. It is based on a series of norms and values. Briefly, ethics is the assessment of the human activities as "right" or "wrong" according to a set of values and norms [Dolasir, S. 2006]. Ethics is the philosophy of moral principles. The concept of "ethics" suggests best "life style" to human being [Yapan, M. T. 2007]. Sport is a game based on physical exertion. Like any game, sport, by its very nature, has rules and principles. Though each single sports branch has variant of rules specific to that branch, there are common basic principles and rules inherent in "sports fact" as a whole, hence, qualifying "sports event" subject matter of ethics. [Erdemli, A. 2006]. 2-4 hour daily training of a child at early age and its contribution to childhood, adolescence and to moral values is an "ethical problem" in general. The reality of "A child grows up through games" transforms into "a child grows up through training" [Sahin, M. 2007]. Quite often, as a result of confusion between determination and greediness, moral values decays and there remains a pseudo-ethics in our hands [Erdemli, A. 2006].

2. Method

Sample data was collected from 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th grade students of four secondary schools geographically located at different regions of Burdur city. The school names in the sample data were excluded and numbers from 1 to 4 were used to refer to schools (Eg: school 1, school 2, ...) throughout the study. Totally 191 students participated in the research, of which 88 were female students (46%) and 103 male students (54%). When examined the distribution of the participant students according to their grade levels, research subjects consisted of 55% 7th grade students (N=104), 23% 8th grade (N=43), 22% 6th grade (N=42), and 1% (N=2) 5th grade respectively.

When analysed the gender and grade levels distribution among the four schools located at different areas, there is no significant difference among the schools in terms of gender, $\chi^2(3, N=191) = 2.33, p=.50$.

This result ensures the heterogeneous distribution of the sample data intended initially. But, when analysed the distribution of the grade levels among the schools, the result is observed to have a significant difference, $\chi^2(9, N=191) = 43.70, p<.001$. However, it is apparent that the difference is insignificant when we evaluate both the impact of this difference ($\eta = .24$), and contingency coefficient obtained from chi square test ($C=.43, p<.001$).

Table 1 indicates the distribution of the grade levels among the schools. It was noticed that existing discrepancy is due to having 2 fifth-grade students from school 3, and no eighth-grade students from the same school. It was decided not to include the fifth-grade students in the analysis. Though there is a similar situation for eighth-grade students, regarding the impact analysis and contingency coefficient results it was decided to use eighth-grades in the comparison among sixth, seventh and eighth grades. However, It was decided that the results should be evaluated at a level (Eg: $p<.0001$) of strict significance.

3. Findings

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distributions of the question of
“I shake hand of the opponent(s) after the competition whether I win or lose”

Frequency	N	%	Valid %	Cumulative
Never	6	3.1	3.1	3.1
Seldom	16	8.4	8.4	11.5
Sometimes	24	12.6	12.6	24.1
Often	33	17.3	17.3	41.4
Always	112	58.6	58.6	100.0
Total	191	100.0	100.0	

When analysed the frequency of hand shaking with the opponents after the competitions, the highest frequency is “always” by 57%. Other frequencies follow as “often” by 17%, “sometimes” by 13%, “seldom” by 8%, and “never” by 3% respectively.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distributions of the question of
“I cheat to win when I feel obliged”

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Never	169	88.5	88.5	88.5
Seldom	12	6.3	6.3	94.8
Sometimes	4	2.1	2.1	96.9
Often	3	1.6	1.6	98.4
Always	3	1.6	1.6	100.0
Total	191	100.0	100.0	

When examined participants cheating behaviour, the highest frequency expressed is “never” by 89%, then “seldom” by 6%, “sometimes” by 2%, “often” and “always” by 1% respectively.

Table 3: Frequency and percentage distributions of the question
*“I congratulate my opponent by complimenting on him/her or using hand signals
for his/her actions”*

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Never	13	6.8	6.8	6.8
Seldom	28	14.7	14.7	21.5
Sometimes	32	16.8	16.8	38.2
Often	32	16.8	16.8	55.0
Always	86	45.0	45.0	100.0
Total	191	100.0	100.0	

When analysed the frequency of the “response behavior” of the participants to opponents' gentle actions, The highest frequency is “always” by 45%, then “often” and “sometimes” by 17%, “seldom” by 15%, and “never” by 7% respectively.

Table 4: Frequency and percentage distributions of the question
“I intervene against the ball harshly to intimidate my opponent”

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Never	74	38.7	38.7	38.7
Seldom	38	19.9	19.9	58.6
Sometimes	25	13.1	13.1	71.7
Often	21	11.0	11.0	82.7
Always	33	17.3	17.3	100.0
Total	191	100.0	100.0	

When analyzed the participants' intimidation behaviour to the opponents, the highest frequency expressed is “never” by 39%. Then, “seldom” by 20%, “always” by 17%, Sometimes by 13% and “often” by 11%.

Table 5: Frequency and percentage distributions of the question
“If my opponent is penalized unjustly, I try to correct the injustice”

	Frequency	%	Valid %
Never	24	12.6	12.6
Seldom	39	20.4	20.4
Sometimes	39	20.4	20.4
Often	33	17.3	17.3
Always	56	29.3	29.3
Total	191	100.	100.0

When analyzed the participants' behaviour about correcting injustice that an opponent undergo, the highest frequency is “always” by 30%, then “seldom” and sometimes by 20%, “often” by 17%, and “never” by 13%.

4. Result and Suggestions

At the end of the result, T-test was performed to observe the students' moral behavior changes according to their gender or not. According to the results of the analysis, there were no differences in the moral behavior of male and female students. For understanding if the age of the students is influenced by moral behavior, 6th, 7th and 8th grade students were compared by making one way diversity analysis. There are significant differences of the moral behavior of the each age of the students and also students who participate in the competitions were compared by T-test. According to the result of T-test, students who participate in competitions have statistically significant differences from those entering physical education classes.

According to this, students who participate in competitions ($X=3.84$, $S=.82$) show more suitable behavior than participant in the physical education lesson ($X=3.50$, $S=.72$). In a study on moral behavior of 12-14 age group in 4 different schools in Burdur City, it was seen that there was no significant differences between male and female students. Because of the 4+4 education system of the Ministry of National Education, 5th grade students have less participant in school teams than others.

School teams usually have 6th, 7th and 8th grade students and younger age groups Show better moral behaviors. When research on the results of the study is compared with research of Çanakkale city and they are similar with each other.

The compulsory physical education period of each grades student in middle school should be increased. Middle school students should be encouraged to participate at sports competitions.

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